

PERCEPTIONS AND UNDERSTANDING OF AGRICULTURAL FIELD WORKERS ON THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE TO THEIR WORKING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

The research study centers on the levels of perceptions and understanding of agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change on their working environment. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed in the study. Data were collected through an adopted and modified survey questionnaire and administered among forty (40) agricultural field workers in Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, Philippines. Descriptive statistics and the Pearson correlation coefficient were utilized in interpreting the data. The study's results revealed that the agricultural field workers' showed a strong positive perception and a very high understanding on the impact of climate change to their working environment. Moreover, the study disclosed a significant relationship between the variables being investigated. Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that the agricultural field workers' understanding and perceptions are both influenced by one another towards the impact of climate change to their working environment. Thus, the institution and agriculture-related departments may encourage the conduct of conferences for further validation of climate change impacts to the working environment and promote programs for shared insights among the related group for the progressive implementation of climate-resilient strategies in the future.

Keywords: *perception, understanding, agricultural field workers, climate change, working environment*

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a global phenomenon that has significantly affected our planet, including different forms of lives within. It refers to a long term shift of temperature and weather patterns which is identified as a deliberate-natural process of our planet in adapting to the changes of inevitable factors such as the earth's orbit, shifts of sun, and emissions from volcanoes. However, as human knowledge advances with time, creating numerous innovations and hacks in living, the nature has been disregarded extremely. With the aid of excessive use of gases, vehicles, and technology, humans aid in speeding up climate change which makes them now as the major cause of this phenomenon. The impacts of climate change are pronounced in the agricultural sector, affecting the livelihoods of millions of farmers and agricultural field workers worldwide as they are the one who's directly involve with the world's natural resources. Mainly, agricultural sector is the direct observer of the climate change's impact, especially the agricultural field workers, since they are vulnerable with the weather and climate as part of their daily living.

Perception and understanding are considered as fundamental aspects of human cognition that aids in the process of knowing and comprehending complex phenomena like climate change. Perception involves interpreting the information received through senses, while understanding is the ability to grasp and comprehend information. The perception and understanding of agricultural field workers plays a crucial role for their livelihood, especially that they are one to observe first the changes in weather and impacts of climate change. Furthermore, they also directly identify posed risk of climate change's impact and usually the one to develop adaptation strategies to protect the crops and plants in their working environment. Thus, perceptions and understanding of agricultural field workers must be measured and identified as to what extent they know about the impact of climate change on their working fields.

Determining the perceptions and understanding of agricultural field workers towards the impact of climate change on their working environment implies the extent of their cognition on the field that they are working every day. Thus, opportunities for future scholars to test the findings of the study in determining the depth among the agricultural field worker's theoretical and practical knowledge in terms of the climate change impacts to their working environment.

Timbal and Serino (2019) stated that climate change influences several sectors including agriculture. Results of their study asserted that farmers have enough knowledge on climate change, which they mostly learned from their own experiences and observation. Others identify garbage that was being burned as a cause, while some include deforestation and overpopulation. However, with these perceptions, there were only a few adaptive plans and strategies that farmers crafted for future impacts of climate change compared to the current implemented strategies (Talanow et al., 2021). Poor livestock health and reduced crop yields were attributed to climate change, yet when asked about changes in livelihood that aren't directed to climate change in the question, groups assign economic, political, and social factors as the cause of changes (Mertz et al., 2009). The results of their study coordinates as the gap that this study will bridge on,

by specifying climate change as the cause of livelihood changes and determining the level of perception and understanding of agricultural field workers towards that change.

This study aims to identify the perceptions and understanding among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment, specifically to identify the extent of their perception and understanding in relation to the field they are exposed.

Research Questions

This study aims to identify the perception and understanding of agricultural field workers in Central Mindanao University on the impact of climate change to their working environment. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of perception among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment?
2. What is the level of understanding among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the perception and understanding among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment?

Hypothesis of the study

From the problem stated above, the hypothesis was formulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the perception and understanding among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers employed a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the relationship between the perception and understanding of agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change on their working environment. The study was conducted in the agricultural fields of Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon, Philippines. It is a university located in the southern part of the country and considered the center of excellence in the field of agricultural education. The gathering of data was directed to the agricultural field workers (farmers, agricultural laborers, and other personnel directly involved in agricultural activities) of the university stationed at different agricultural sectors, namely: the animal production project, the plant nursery and plantation, and the Agricultural Experiment Center. A random sampling technique was used in identifying the participants of the study. Thus, a total of forty (40) agricultural field workers served as the participants of the study. The research utilized adopted, modified, and validated survey questionnaire from Gemeda (2015). The questionnaire obtained a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.779 which signifies the reliability of the questionnaire. This questionnaire measures the perception and understanding of agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change on their working environment. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used in interpreting the gathered data. On the other

hand, the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine any relationship among the variables being investigated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Field workers' perception on the impact of climate change to their working environment.

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTION RATING	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
Temperature getting warmer in your working environment	4.57	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
Rainfall fluctuations is occurring in your working environment	4.87	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
Pattern of weather is changing in your working environment	4.82	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
Climate change is happening in your working environment	4.57	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
Climate change is a real problem in your working environment	4.17	Agree	Positive Perception
Climate change reduce crop production	4.55	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
Climate change affect your working environment	4.52	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
You understand the causes of global warming	4.10	Agree	Positive Perception
Global warming affect our way of life	4.62	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
Your family believe that climate change is a serious problem in your working environment	4.32	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
Over-all Mean Interpretation	4.51	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception

Legend:

Range	Description rating	Qualitative Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Strong Positive Perception
3.41-4.20	Agree	Positive Perception
2.61-3.40	Undecided	Lack of Opinion
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Negative Perception
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Strong Negative Perception

The level of perception of agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change on their working environment is shown in Table 1. As projected in the table, eight (8) indicators entail strongly agree, and two (2) indicator states agree. It has an overall mean score of 4.51, indicating “strong positive perception,” which implies that farmers significantly acknowledge the impact of climate change on their farming environment and practices.

This result is in parallel to the findings of Talanow et al. (2021), as their study stated how farmers perceive climate change. They found out that most farmers observed long-term regional changes in climate, including rainfall patterns, temperature variation, and extreme climatic events. Thus, farmers are perceptive of their working environment based on how they describe their observations on the field. Furthermore, Arbuckle et al. (2015) revealed that farmers who trusted environmental groups, bringing along their beliefs, were more likely to perceive climate change as a threat, influencing their support for adaptation strategies. Thus, this suggests a positive perception of the farmers in their capacity to respond to climate challenges in their environment. In the same vein, Ullah et al. (2015) also state that majority of their respondents allocate climate change with reasonable risk to their lives as perceived by them, which defines that climate change impact is strongly perceptible to individuals, especially farmers.

Table 2. Field workers’ understanding on the impact of climate change to their working environment.

INDICATORS	MEAN	DESCRIPTION RATING	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
You understand the difference between weather and climate	3.60	Agree	High Understanding
Climate change is human induced	4.05	Agree	High Understanding
Climate change affects health conditions	4.75	Strongly Agree	Very High Understanding
Climate change can disturb ecosystem services	4.40	Strongly Agree	Very High Understanding
Floods after rains are common in your in your working environment	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very High Understanding
Floods after rains are common in your in your working environment	4.45	Strongly Agree	Very High Understanding
Over-all Mean Interpretation	4.25	Strongly Agree	Very High Understanding

Legend:

Range	Descriptive range	Qualitative Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Understanding
3.41-4.20	Agree	High Understanding
2.61-3.40	Undecided	Moderate Understanding
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low Understanding
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Understanding

Table 2 revealed the understanding of the field workers on the impact of climate change on their working environment. The findings exposed that four (4) indicators above entail strongly agree, while two (2) indicator revealed agree. Based on the mean of means value that has a score of 4.25, the understanding of agricultural field workers towards the impact of climate change on their working environment reached a very high level of understanding, which implies that they are well informed as to how climate change impacts are associated with the environmental changes in their work fields.

The result is supported by the findings of Muller and Shackleton (2014), which state that commercial farmers are well informed regarding the effects of climate change in terms of their vulnerability. They have great experience in dealing with marginal conditions, which entails greater adaptivity and responsiveness to environmental changes. On the other hand, Karki et al. (2019) revealed in their study that many farmers worldwide have noticed changes such as rising temperatures and unpatterned rainfall, which have led to reduced agricultural production. It emphasizes that farmers' understanding plays a crucial role in adaptation measures.

Table 3. Correlation analysis on perception and understanding among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment.

INDICATORS	CORRELATION	PROBABILITY
Understanding	0.668(**)	.000

****.** *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)*

The relationship between the perception and understanding of agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change on their working environment is presented in Table 3. The two (2) variables, perceptions and understanding, entail a significant correlation of 0.668 and are significant at the 0.01 level. The result showed a significant positive correlation, which means that the greater the degree or level of perception, the greater the degree or level of understanding. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis of the study, which states that there is no significant relationship between the perceptions and understanding among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment.

This finding substantiated the global survey of Bayer's "Farmer Voice" in 2023, which highlighted that farmers who perceived climate change's impact were more likely to take proactive steps to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions and adapt their practices, indicating a clear link between their understanding of climate change and their willingness to implement changes in response to its effects. Also, according to Amadou et al. (2022), perception has a crucial role for farmers in their adaptation strategies. It was revealed that farmers who perceived climate change impacts on their immediate environment show a firmer understanding and intention to engage in adaptation programs.

Conclusions

The researchers conclude that agricultural field workers have a strong positive perception of the impact of climate change on their working environment. On the other hand, they have a very high level of understanding on the impact of climate change to their working environment. Furthermore, there is a significant positive relationship between perception and understanding, thus rejecting the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the perceptions and understanding among agricultural field workers on the impact of climate change to their working environment.

Recommendations

The study suggest that the institution may encourage the conduct of conferences for agricultural field workers to further validate the impact of climate change to their working environment. Moreover, agriculture-related groups and committees may also promote programs where agricultural field workers can share their understanding to the implementing committee for a more progressive implementation of climate-resilient strategies. Lastly, the researchers suggest that future scholars may delve deeper into the theoretical and practical knowledge of agricultural field workers regarding the impact of climate change on their working environment, in order to gain further insights.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher observed proper ethics in conducting the research with the agricultural field workers in Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Maramag, Bukidnon, Philippines. First, a letter from the Dean was obtained to secure course procedure in conducting the research survey. Secondly, a consent form from the participants was collected, and presented as proof to certify that the conduct of the research was valid. Thirdly, the time and availability of the participants were prioritized and observed and were paved the way only during their vacant time based on their schedules. Fourth, the confidentiality of the identity and gathered data was secured and had been only used for academic purposes. Interpretation of the gathered data adhered to the participants' privacy and was stated without partiality. Lastly, plagiarism was strictly observed in the interpretation and encoding of the data as appropriate technology was utilized to detect and avoid such offenses.

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